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Here is the complete blue print of collatz with testable functions.

This document is intended to provide a complete working sketch of collatz as currently i don't have and working with mobile device so i am attaching all my hand written work here in a way that even a child will understand how collatz function.

Position Mapping.

7 mod 8 class (Apply collatz)		3 mod 8 class (Apply collatz)	
Position		Position	
1	7 → 11	1	3 → 5
2	15 → 23	2	11 → 17
3	23 → 35	3	19 → 29
4	31 → 47	4	27 → 41
5	39 → 59	5	35 → 53
6	47 → 71	6	43 → 65
7	55 → 83	7	51 → 77
8	63 → 95	8	59 → 89
9	71 → 107	9	67 → 101
10	79 → 119	10	75 → 113

- * Position of 7 mod 8 class Mapping in 3 mod 5 in Order.
- * Even Positions are Mapping inside class.

$$1 \rightarrow 2$$

$$3 \rightarrow 5$$

$$5 \rightarrow 8$$

$$7 \rightarrow 11$$

$$f_n = \frac{3n+1}{2}$$

$$2 \rightarrow 3$$

$$4 \rightarrow 6 \rightarrow 9$$

$$8 \rightarrow 12 \rightarrow 18 \rightarrow 27$$

$f_n = 3n/2$ until odd

Example. $8 \times 3/2 = 24/2 = 12$

$$12 \times 3/2 = 36/2 = 18$$

$$18 \times 3/2 = 54/2 = 27$$

* 12
For next position in even case just change 2 with 3.

Short cut. $8 = 2 \times 2 \times 2$
Next position = $3 \times 3 \times 3$
 $4 = 2 \times 2$

See examples →

Next position = 3×3
 $6 = 2 \times 3$ Next position 3×3

Blue Print of Collatz.

All mappings and functions are derived using techniques shown on Page 1. All odd numbers are divided into 4 classes.

Class	$1 \pmod 8$	$3 \pmod 8$	$5 \pmod 8$	$7 \pmod 8$
Calculate	$\frac{n+7}{8}$	$\frac{n+5}{8}$	$\frac{n+3}{8}$	$\frac{n+1}{8}$
Position	8	8	8	8
Calculate	$8n-7$	$8n-5$	$8n-3$	$8n-1$
Number				$8n-1$

- * Sorry note book is not allowing for to correct typos. Calculate any Position of any class and start applying these Rules.

Class Rule Return Position in Next Rule to Apply.

- * Ah again Miss one column. Now we will see the set of rules on next page.
- * I currently have no access to laptop so I have to use old method.

So once you calculate Position start applying a set of Rules written on next page.

- * Also $7 \pmod 8$ class only interact to outside on odd positions so if Position function Return even value make it odd first.

- * To see how to make it odd see Page 1.

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Rules:

Class	Position	Rule Apply.	Return Position	Next Rule to Apply.
$7 \pmod 8$	Odd	$(3n+1)/2$	$3 \pmod 8$	Apply Rules of $3 \pmod 8$ class on Returned Position
	if even make odd			
$3 \pmod 8$	if odd	$(3n-1)/2$	$5 \pmod 8$	$5 \pmod 8$ rules.
	if even	$3n/2$	$1 \pmod 8$	$1 \pmod 8$ rules.
$1 \pmod 8$	if $1 \pmod 4$	$(3n+1)/4$	$1 \pmod 8$	$1 \pmod 8$ rules.
	if $2 \pmod 4$	$(3n-3)/4$	$7 \pmod 8$	$7 \pmod 8$ rules.
	if $3 \pmod 4$	$(3n-1)/4$	$5 \pmod 8$	$5 \pmod 8$ rules.
	if $0 \pmod 4$	$3n/4$	$3 \pmod 8$	$3 \pmod 8$ rules.
$5 \pmod 8$	if $3 \pmod 8$	$(3n+7)/8$	$5 \pmod 8$	$5 \pmod 8$ rules.
	if $2 \pmod 8$	$(3n+2)/8$	$5 \pmod 8$	$5 \pmod 8$ rules.
	if $4 \pmod 8$	$(3n+4)/8$	$3 \pmod 8$	$3 \pmod 8$ rules.
	if $6 \pmod 8$	$(3n+6)/8$	$1 \pmod 8$	$1 \pmod 8$ rule.
	if $0 \pmod 8$	$3n/8$	$7 \pmod 8$	$7 \pmod 8$ rule.
	if $1 \pmod 16$	$(3n+13)/16$	$1 \pmod 8$	$1 \pmod 8$ rules.
	if $5 \pmod 16$	$(3n+1)/16$	$7 \pmod 8$	$7 \pmod 8$ rules.
	if $9 \pmod 16$	$(3n+5)/16$	$5 \pmod 8$	$5 \pmod 8$ rules.
	if $13 \pmod 16$	$(3n+9)/16$	$3 \pmod 8$	$3 \pmod 8$ rules.

 $(n+1)/8$

These are the set of all rules working beneath collatz function.

Completely predictable and deterministic.

No number can diverge from these rules.

Example on how to use functions

What you see collatz is doing verses what it actually do. We will pick a smaller number that will visit all classes. but drop quickly as I have to do by hand.
 $N = 15 \pmod{8}$ class.

$$15 \times 3 + 1 = 46/2^k$$

$$23 \times 3 + 1 = 70/2^k$$

$$35 \times 3 + 1 = 106/2^k$$

$$53 \times 3 + 1 = 160/2^k$$

$$5 \times 3 + 1 = 16/2^k$$

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	Position	Rule	Resulting class	Number,
	2	$3P/2$	3 still in Same class	$8 \cdot 3 - 1 = 23$
	3	$3 \cdot 3 + 1/2$	5 in $3 \pmod{8}$ mod 8 class	$8 \cdot 5 - 5 = 35$
	5	$3 \cdot 5 - 1/2$	7 in $5 \pmod{8}$	$8 \cdot 7 - 3 = 53$ 53 7 is
	7	$(7+1)/8$	7 1 in $1 \pmod{8}$ its terminal.	3 mod 4 in $5 \pmod{8}$ class So look for 3 mod 4 Rules in $5 \pmod{8}$ class

Yes its not easy to do by hand but I did it just to show how this function is working inside.

So all we need to calculate position and start applying rules depending on position and its modular class. See what I need to write under 7 I wrote under 53. Forgive it. You can skip number calculation. So once in next class we will apply rules of next class. Every path is fully deterministic and underneath there is no chaos. Will see you someday with prime patterns.

Collatz tree

Not so neat and clean, Sorry for inconvenience
 I am bed bound patient doing all by lying on bed
 without any laptop living in stone age 😊

	$5 \pmod 8$	$4(3n+1)$	loop class	
1	$5 \rightarrow 16$	4×4	$2^4 \rightarrow 1$ *	$3 - 1$
2	$13 \rightarrow 40$	4×10	$2^3 \times 5$ *	$7 - 2$
3	$21 \rightarrow 64$	4×16	$2^6 \rightarrow 1$	$11 - 3$
4	$29 \rightarrow 88$	4×22	$2^3 \times 11$ *	$15 - 4$
5	$37 \rightarrow 112$	4×28	$2^4 \times 7$ *	$19 - 5$
6	$45 \rightarrow 136$	4×34	$2^3 \times 17$ *	order
7	$53 \rightarrow 160$	4×40	$2^4 \times 5$	$i = \frac{n+1}{4}$
8	$61 \rightarrow 184$	4×46	$2^3 \times 23$	
9	$69 \rightarrow 208$	4×52	$2^4 \times 13$ *	order Mapping back rules:
10	$77 \rightarrow 232$	4×58	$2^3 \times 29$	
11	$85 \rightarrow 256$	4×64	$2^8 \times 1$	$2 - 1$
12	$93 \rightarrow 280$	4×70	$2^3 \times 35$	$10 - 4$
13	$101 \rightarrow 304$	4×76	$2^4 \times 19$	$19 - 7$
14	$109 \rightarrow 328$	4×82	$2^3 \times 41$	
15	$117 \rightarrow 352$	4×88	$2^5 \times 11$	$1 \pmod 4$
16	$125 \rightarrow 376$	4×94	$2^3 \times 47$	1
17	$133 \rightarrow 400$	4×100	$2^4 \times 25$	5
18	$141 \rightarrow 424$	4×106	$2^3 \times 53$	
19	$149 \rightarrow 448$	4×112	$2^6 \times 7$	
20	$157 \rightarrow 472$	4×118	$2^3 \times 59$	
21	$165 \rightarrow 496$	4×124	$2^4 \times 31$	
22	$173 \rightarrow 520$	4×130	$2^3 \times 65$	
23	$181 \rightarrow 544$	4×136	$2^5 \times 17$	
24	$189 \rightarrow 568$	4×142	$2^3 \times 71$	
25	197 $\rightarrow 592$	4×148	$2^4 \times 37$	
26	$205 \rightarrow 616$	4×154	$2^3 \times 77$	
27	$213 \rightarrow 640$	4×160	$2^7 \times 5$	
28	$221 \rightarrow 664$	4×166	$2^3 \times 83$	
29	$229 \rightarrow 688$	4×172	$2^4 \times 43$	

key insights.

- * All Position has different entry and exit paths in other modular class except $1 \pmod 8$ Return it 1st position on its 1st position (Only loop) and $5 \pmod 8$ Return 1st position of $1 \pmod 8$ on its first position (we enter in loop through 5)
- * Collatz is all about the transition between modular classes under strict but mapable rules.
- * Different paths of entry and exit prevents any Non trivial cycle.
- * Divergence through $7 \pmod 8$ class is weaker than convergence through $5 \pmod 8$ class. Here's why.
 - $7 \pmod 8$ class is only class that give consecutive even ~~odd~~ steps in row (as we seen it do on even positions) but it force to go to convergence paths after finite steps. Whereas $3 \pmod 4$ positions in $5 \pmod 8$ loop back into $5 \pmod 8$ infinitely.
- * $5 \pmod 8$ class act as original function that keep looping back into itself always with higher divisibility power. No such pattern has been found in $7 \pmod 8$ class yet.

Final words.

Collatz is highly organised and deterministic structure, its keeping it work since 80 years will hold it ~~in~~ ever.

- * Any confusion about $5 \pmod 8$ class could be resolved while looking its structure.

There might be some confusion as work isn't very neat but I hope the one who gives just 20% attention will understand it. All functions and rules have been derived from position mapping. 100% deterministic, testable and predictable.

We can do same with $3\text{mod}4$ and $1\text{mod}4$ classes but that wouldn't be clean so i used the most neat clean and compressed system.

Any further work built on my idea need citation.

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Thankyou.